

Social Causes of Abortion in Tanzania

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Abstract

The article "Social Causes of Abortion in Tanzania" explores the multifaceted social factors contributing to abortion rates in the country. It highlights the interplay of cultural, educational, and systemic challenges that influence the decision to terminate a pregnancy. Juvenile delinquency and truancy, compounded by a lack of comprehensive sex education, create an environment where adolescents are ill-prepared to navigate sexual health. The pressures of academic achievement further complicate this landscape, as many young people feel compelled to prioritize schooling over parenting. Limited access to reproductive health services exacerbates the issue, with many women unable to obtain necessary information or support.

Fear of stigma and discrimination plays a crucial role, as societal attitudes towards single motherhood and abortion lead to social exclusion and negative stereotypes, increasing the burdens felt by women. Additionally, peer pressure, along with familial and relationship dynamics, such as pressure from boyfriends or physicians, further complicates personal decision-making. The article also discusses the implications of timing and the physician's role in oversimplifying abortion procedures, contributing to the dilemma faced by women. By examining these intertwined social causes, the article aims to shed light on the broader societal context influencing abortion in Tanzania, ultimately calling for more inclusive policies and support systems that address these pressing issues. Through a deeper understanding of these factors, stakeholders can better advocate for reproductive and comprehensive health education, fostering a more supportive environment for the lives of women and youth.

Introduction

Abortion, is real in Tanzania, just as it is in other parts of the World. It is a deeply contentious and multifaceted issue, operates at the intersection of various social motives, particularly among vulnerable populations like juvenile delinquents and those at the verge of poverty and those facing academic truancy in schools. The precipitants of these circumstances are often rooted in insufficient access to comprehensive sex education, which leaves many young individuals ill-equipped with the knowledge of their reproductive health, thereby exacerbating the likelihood of unintended pregnancies. Academic pressures further complicate this landscape, where students grapple with

the demands of succeeding in school while confronting the realities of an un expected pregnancy associated with stigma. Limited access to reproductive health services can intensify these challenges, leaving young people with few resources as they seek information and support. Additionally, fear of societal stigma and discrimination can drive individuals to make choices in isolation, amplifying their sense of social exclusion. Peer influence plays a pivotal role as individuals may feel pressured to conform to the expectations of friends or partners, further complicating their decision-making.

The pressures associated with single motherhood add additional layers of complexity, particularly when

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societal norms and neo-stereotypes perpetuate judgements surrounding young parents. Family dynamics can also exert immense pressure, as individuals may feel compelled to consider familial expectations against their own aspirations and desires. Furthermore, the interaction between healthcare providers and patients may also play a significant role; for instance, physicians may oversimplify the abortion procedure, influencing the patient's perception of the consequences. Collectively these factors illustrate a nuanced web as social motives surrounding abortion, particularly for those already marginalized by their circumstances. Understanding these dynamics is crucial in addressing both the immediate and systemic drivers of reproductive choices among young people.

Social Causes

In Tanzania, social motives for abortion are complex and multifaceted, influenced by a combination of cultural, religious, economic and political factors. Some of the motives are such as: economic pressures, in which many women in Tanzania face significant economic challenges, including poverty, lack of education and limited employment opportunities. Abortion may be seen as a means to avoid financial burdens associated with raising a child. Many women may seek abortions to space out their children or limit the number of children they have due to economic or educational constraints. In some communities' abortion is stigmatized, and women may fear being ostracized or shamed by family, friends or community members if their pregnancy is overt.

*"Waziri wa Afya, Maendeleo ya Jamii, Jinsia Wazee na Watoto, Ummu Mwalimu amesema, bila kuwapeleka wazazi mahakamani na kuhukumiwa kifungo, ndoa za utotoni hazuwezi kukomeshwa. Kwa mujibu wa mtafiti Dkt Lucas Kagera wa shirika lisilo la kiserikali la utafiti REPOA, inakadiriwa watoto 36 kati ya miamoja huolewa kabla ya kufikisha miaka kumi na nane na wengine 27 kati ya mia hupata mimba kabla ya kufikisha miaka 18, huku mikoa ya Shinyanga na Mara ikiongoza kwa kuwa na idadi kubwa ya ndoa za utotoni."*¹.

¹ Translation: The Minister of Health, Community Development, Gender, Elderly and Children, Ummu Mwalimu has said that without taking the parents to court and sentencing them to prison, child marriages cannot be stopped. According to researcher Dr. Lucas Kagera of the non-governmental research organization REPOA, which is the major stake holder in the study of early marriages, it is estimated that 36 out of one hundred children get married before reaching the age of eighteen, and another 27 out of a hundred get pregnant, before reaching the age of 18, with

In some cultures, in Tanzania, the norms on marriage and child bearing women are forced to marry before the average age. Abortions have been common in child marriages, the women who are not ready for mother hood.

Society in today's world have plenty of children who seem to be a burden to the individuals and to the society that is the reason women are moved to kill the fetus. This is a global massive plight to the unborn. The society is threatened by its own offspring and due to some reasons it kills them. Our society either closes eyes or encourages one's own personal self-precedence over the selves of others. This is an evil per se and unacceptable. To deny the coming up of a new life is to be self - cantered. It we were created without any merit from our creator, why should we block other lives from coming into existence?

Sociological point of view considers people, and mostly the youth and those in schools and colleges performing an abortion in an attempt to secure their carriers as students. They fear to lose school and jobs because of pregnancy, so they opt to abort.

"Social pressure²" from the parents of the girl in fear of shame guilt feelings and bad names from the society, lead to abortion. Boys also force their pregnant girls to do abortion. They do not want or they are not ready to be fathers and rise up a family. However, girls in their pre-marital sexual intercourses when impregnated, end up in doing abortion due to the fact that, they fear to be expelled from their homes by their parents. Moreover, the other reasons may be, they want to continue with the pleasure without accountability; they want to remain young girls not mothers.

Married couples in the name of family planning, do abortion to maintain the number of children they want. Married women also, in their infidelity to their husbands go outside marriage or use contraceptives and when they become pregnant, they solve the 'problem' by doing abortion.

Finally, disbelief, anger, bitterness and disappointment of the woman with a pregnancy are the other reasons and justifications which can lead convince some to do abortion.

Shinyanga and Mara regions leading the way in having a large number of child marriages, Cf., DINA, CHALALI, VOA, Ummu Mwalimu, Apendekeza Dawa ya Mimba za Utotoni, Cf., <https://www.voaswahili.com>, (accessed on 20th July 2024).

² Social Pressure is the influence exerted by a group or society on an individual or another group to comply with particular norms or behaviors. Cf., <https://www.psychologydictionary.org>, (accessed on 20th Oct, 2023).

Juvenile Delinquency and Truancy

Human beings' growth development at some stage, especially the youth, may be attracted to try everything and seek to see the reaction. Whatever they see and hear they are motivated to practice it. This behavior pattern leads to naughty behavior patterns and breaking of certain societal rules. Juvenile delinquency therefore can be described as:

"A behavior pattern related to breaking certain rules in the family, in the community or in the society. Offenses will range from violating the discipline at home, truancy, stealing with or without violence, robbery, school strikes, disobedience and other anti-social activities. Delinquent behavior is also called deviant behavior. Examples of this are: stealing, drinking alcohol, rape, smoking, and drug abuse" [3].

Causes of delinquency are numerous; The demands or a peer group to achieve certain things to prove themselves and establish an identity may lead to juvenile delinquency. A social environment may cause such problems to arise e.g. slum areas are associated with delinquency. When moral standards at home, schools and in society are in conflict, may confuse youths as to what are the best rules acceptable by the society to be observed. Lack of parental care, misunderstanding in the family and family quarrels may as well contribute to delinquency.

It can as well come as a result of psychological problems such as fights, frustrations, worries, needs which are not met and inhibitions, poor relationships between youths and their parents. "Strictness and an authoritative attitude of parents towards youths may cause delinquency" [3]. Other forces in schools or in society, to mention just a few of them, may cause some needs to arise and bad feelings which may lead to delinquent behavior. It is reported that abortions are very common from primary to university level, these abortions are most likely forced by parents.

Lack of Comprehensive Sex Education

One reason is the inadequate provision of comprehensive sex education within the school system. The lack of comprehensive information about reproductive health, and the risk of contraceptives leave students ill-informed and more susceptible to unintended pregnancies. It is obvious that the friendships among many students in schools are not healthy, and most of them leads to sexual relationships. Students have to understand that 'true love waits (TLW)³. Various dictionaries define chastity as sexual self-control.

"This control is an ongoing activity throughout a young person's life. Even in marriage the control is necessary. The goal of True Love Waits Campaign is to restore our knowledge, perception and understanding of sex - primarily as a means of procreation and secondly as a sure means of establishing an emotional bond between a man and a woman joined in holy matrimony as instituted by God" [3].

Without access to comprehensive sexual education, young people may lack accurate information about reproductive health and pregnancy prevention through abstinence. This lack of knowledge can lead to unintended pregnancies and a higher likelihood of seeking abortions as a result. In the absence of comprehensive sexual education, myths, misconceptions and stigmatization surrounding abortion may prevail. These pushes individuals toward seeking clandestine procedures of abortion putting their health and lives at risk.

Education system and educational aspirations can be considered as a contributing factors to the occurrence of abortion among youths in Tanzania schools. Here is an explanation of how the education career can be one of the causes of abortion, and why it may be so.

Schooling and Pressure to Succeed Academically

Tanzanian society, has often been having a high emphasis on academic achievement and pursuit of a successful education career. Students may feel immense pressure to excel academically, leading them to prioritize their education over other aspects of their lives, including the use of artificial contraceptive methods. In Tanzania the law these days do allow pregnant students at primary and secondary level. This could be a reason for students and pupils not to be keen and find themselves indulging into premature sexual contact resulting to pregnancy and abortion due lack of marital experience and failure to handle pregnancy crisis.

Limited Access to Reproductive Health Services

Evidences reveal that the youths in schools face limited access to reproductive health education services and provisions, these includes lack of sanitary towels. Other challenges include limited access to medical advice, or counselling, which can further compound the likelihood of unplanned pregnancies and subsequent decisions regarding abortion.

Single mothers in Tanzania, especially those in villages, experience limited access to healthcare resources such as health care facilities, child care services, and social welfare programs. Such reasons discourage women to carry their pregnancy to full term. Moreover,

³ True Love Waits (TLW) – Is a campaign of young people by young people advocating and promoting the virtue of chastity [9].

expectants travel a long distance before they can access a clinic or hospital. The lack of these resources can create additional barriers to single motherhood and have increased the tendency to consider abortion as an alternative. Some women do give birth before they reach the hospital, and yet some others loose either their lives, or the lives of their babies during delivery.

The lack of prenatal care is essential for ensuring a healthy pregnancy and reducing the risk of complications. When an individual faces barrier to accessing prenatal services, they may be unaware of any potential health issues or risks during pregnancy, which can influence their decision to seek an abortion. Addressing the barriers to accessing reproductive health services is critical in reducing the abortion tendency in Tanzania. By improving access to "natural family planning" [1], prenatal care and comprehensive sexual education, individuals become more safe and settled.

Fear of Stigma and Discrimination

Tanzanian society still holds some stigma and discrimination towards young people who engage in sexual activities, and more so to those who happen to be impregnated while in school for that would mean discontinuation. This fear of social shaming and the potential negative consequences, such as being expelled from school or facing judgment from peers, parents and teachers, contributes to the decision to seek abortion. Students abort because of the fear of being punished by parents and educators.

Fear of stigma and discrimination can create a sense of shame and guilt in individuals who are considering abortion, especially if they are devoted Catholics. This internal conflict between personal beliefs and societal pressures can lead individuals to feel isolated and overwhelmed, potentially influencing their decision in seeking an abortion.

Individuals facing unintended pregnancies may fear lack of support and co-operation from their religious community. The fear of judgment and rejection may push individuals toward seeking abortions as a way to avoid social stigma and maintain their relationships within their faith community. In most cases girls who happen to be pregnant outside marriage feel isolated from WAWATA, the Catholic women association of Tanzania.

Fear of stigma and discrimination has brought an impact to individuals spiritual well-being by creating inner turmoil and conflict with their religious beliefs. This internal struggle has brought the feelings of alienation from their faith community and spiritual beliefs potentially influencing their decision - making process regarding abortion.

Call for compassion and support towards individuals facing difficult decisions, including those related to unintended pregnancies is an inevitable step to

undertake. Creating a supportive and understanding environment within Catholic communities can help individuals navigate their options with guidance and care, reducing the fear of stigma and discrimination associated with seeking abortion.

Lack of Support Systems

History has it that; the Catholic support systems began with education, and health services that provided health facilities in both urban and rural areas in Tanzania. Ever since, the emphasis on life has been vital and all that hinders life has always been discouraged. Alternatives to abortion has been a focus, and offering compassion, understanding, and practical assistance to individuals facing difficult circumstances, such as unintended pregnancies has been not overlooked. While the Catholic Church upholds the sanctity of life and opposes abortion, she also recognizes the importance of supporting individuals in crisis with love and care.

In 1954 the British Colonial government allowed the Church to continue to provide medical care so much that by 1961, the Church already had 23 general hospitals and 8 health centers. Currently, this Church in Tanzania owns one zonal consultant referral hospital, six regional hospitals, 19 Council designated hospitals, 29 voluntary agency hospitals, 94 health centers and 338 dispensaries" [7].

Catholic crisis pregnancy centers can be established to offer a counselling, emotional support, and practical assistance to individuals facing unplanned pregnancies. These places could provide resources, information, parenting classes, material support such as baby supplies, and referrals to healthcare care services for individuals considering alternatives to abortion.

Maternity wards in Catholic hospitals have to intensify and improve services, care and support. These maternities are to offer a safe and nurturing environment where women can receive help during their pregnancies and after giving birth.

Nurses and other health care attendants should show tenderly love and compassion.

In the Catholic context, the lack of support systems such as post abortion healing, family support programs, adoption services, affordable maternity homes, and crisis pregnancy centers can accelerate abortion tendencies among girls and women in Tanzania today by creating barriers to seeking alternatives to abortion and contributing to feelings of isolation and desperation. Here are some ways in which the lack of support systems can impact individuals:

The lack of supportive networks can contribute to emotional distress and isolation for girls and women facing unintended pregnancies. Without access to compassionate support or guidance, individuals may feel overwhelmed, alone and unsure where to turn for

help, increasing the likelihood of seeking abortions as a means to cope with their difficult circumstances.

"The Church will work through small Christian communities to strengthen the capacity of families and children and enhance values and moral to ensure everyone's safety. We commit to familiarize ourselves with Church and civil documents on safeguarding and engage with our communities to promote awareness and education on child safeguarding. This includes workshops, seminars, and informational campaigns designed to foster a culture of vigilance and care" [5]. Without access to compassionate care, accurate information, and quality healthcare services, individuals may put their health and lives at risk by seeking unsafe procedures, further exacerbating the negative consequences of the lack of support systems. Students facing unintended pregnancies may lack appropriate support from family or friends, or guidance from school staff and in most cases they feel out of place and decide to drop school. Without adequate support, individuals may feel overwhelmed, and the options for abortion might be seen as a way to address the situation discreetly and avoid potential judgment or negative consequences. In almost all Tanzanian schools' students who happen to be pregnant are now allowed to proceed with studies, only those who decide on their own to drop studies with feelings of being misfits opt to exclude themselves from school.

In addressing the lack of support systems that can accelerate abortion tendencies among girls and women in Tanzania with the Catholic community, it is crucial to promote compassion, understanding and non-judgmental care within religious communities. By creating supportive networks, offering guidance, and advocating for access to resources and reproductive health services, the Catholic Church can play a pivotal role in helping individuals facing unintended pregnancies make informed and supported decisions that align with Church values and beliefs.

Peer Pressure and Influence

The influence of peers and the desire to fit in or engage in risky behavior can contribute to increased sexual activity and a higher likelihood of unintended pregnancies among students. Peer pressure can potentially make it more difficult for individuals to make informed decisions.

"Peer pressure is internal or external pressure felt to behave in certain ways both good and bad. peer pressure begins as early as ten with the forming of social groups in elementary school and increases during adolescence, throughout junior and high school. Negative peer pressure can encourage teenagers to participate in negative behaviors and habits, such as: skipping class, stealing, cheating bullying and using drugs or alcohol" [9].

Such influence can contribute to abortion tendencies among the youths in Tanzania in several ways: The desire for acceptance: Youths may feel pressured to conform to the beliefs and behavior of their peers in order to gain acceptance and approval. If abortion is perceived as a common or acceptable choice among peers, individuals may be more likely to consider it as an option, especially if they believe it will help them fit in or avoid being judged by their peers.

Lack of accurate information is another factor accelerating abortion among the youths. Peers can play a significant role in shaping individual's attitudes and beliefs about abortion by sharing misinformation or partial truths. If youths receive inaccurate information about abortion from their peers, they may be more likely to make decisions based on misconceptions rather than factual knowledge, potentially leading them to consider abortion without fully understanding the implications.

Fear of exclusion: The youths may fear being ostracized or excluded from their social circles if they do not conform to the group's beliefs or behaviors including attitudes towards abortion. This fear of rejection can create pressure to align with peer opinions and choices, even if it goes against their personal values or beliefs ultimately influencing their decision-making regarding abortion.

Peer groups tend to normalize risky behavior and underestimate the consequences resulted by them. Such normalized risky behaviors are casual or loose relationships, which may also contribute to such a culture where abortion is seen as a common and easy solution to unintended pregnancies. If youths are surrounded by peers who engage in behaviors that increase the risk of unplanned pregnancies, they may be more likely to view abortion as a quick fix to avoid perceived consequences.

Peers can have emotional influence on individual's decision making process, especially during times of vulnerability or uncertainty. If youths receive encouragement or support from their peers to consider abortion as a viable option, they may be swayed by emotional appeals or the desire to seek validation from their social group, potentially leading them to choose abortion without fully exploring other alternatives.

Addressing these impacts of peer pressure and influence on abortion tendencies among youths in Tanzania, it is essential to promote education, awareness and open dialogue about reproductive health, sexual education, and the adverse consequences of abortion. By providing accurate information, fostering critical thinking skills and encouraging respectful communication within peer groups, we can empower youths to make profound decisions based on their values, beliefs, and well-being.

Single Motherhood

Basic needs of any child start with a family where both parents cooperate harmoniously in its upbringing. Both parents have the right and the duty to devote themselves to the rearing and education of the children they are responsible for bringing into the world. "Where either parent neglects this duty, a serious wrong is done to the other parent and the child" [10]. Single motherhood is that to the situation where a woman becomes a mother and raises a child or children without a partner or spouse. It can occur due to various circumstances such as divorce, separation, the death of partner, or choosing to parent alone. "The tendency for girls to have children outside marriage is, therefore, one that should be opposed by all. It is true that motherhood has a value; but this is within the context of the family" [10]. Single mothers in Tanzania, especially those in villages, experience limited access to resources such as health care facilities, child care services, and social welfare programs. Expectants travel a long distance before they can access a clinic or hospital. The lack of these resources can create additional barriers to single motherhood and increase the tendency to consider abortion as an alternative. Some women do give birth before they reach the hospital, and yet some others loose either their lives, or the lives of their babies.

"It is not enough that the mother provides food, shelter and education for her child; the child needs also the care of a father and, if this is missing, the child always suffers. In addition to this it must, of course, be clearly understood that the act of intercourse outside marriage is gravely sinful" [10].

When both parents are working away from home, the children are left under the guidance and care of another child. Or when it happens that a parent is a single mother, the upbringing of a kid will definitely lack some upbringing initial formation necessary for her growth and crucial for his or her future growth.

"This is a twofold injustice: it is unfair to those in charge and to those who have to be tended. Even when competent persons are entrusted with the care of the children, they are not an adequate substitute for the parents" [10].

Parents who give their time and talents to their home and family are not depriving their family by not earning salaries. On the contrary they are making a very significant contribution to their children in a way that no money can supply [10]. Relationship between single motherhood and abortion tendencies in Tanzania, can be manifested in several factors.

⁴ Nuclear family, in anthropology refers to a group of people who are united by ties of partnership and parenthood and consisting of a pair of adults and their socially recognized children. Typically, but not always,

Single mothers especially those who are young and still in studies may face financial challenges expected from family, friends, and the community in providing them with their children with basic needs. On the other hand, they are at this incident regarded as prostitute and not keen. This financial strain can influence the tendency to consider abortion as a means of avoiding the additional financial responsibility and potential hardships associated with raising a child alone.

Societal Stigma

Being cut off from the community circle, they may face social stigma and a lack of support from the family, friends and the community. The absence of a reliable support system can make the decision to continue a pregnancy and raise a child as a single mother seem overwhelming. This may therefore lead to some single mothers to consider abortion as a response to the perceived lack of support. Single mothers especially those who are students or pursuing carrier goals, may perceive having a child as a potential barrier to their educational and potential barrier to their educational and professional aspirations. The fear of compromising their educational or carrier opportunities can influence the tendency to consider abortion as a way to preserve these goals.

"Societal stigma refers to the negative attitudes, beliefs and stereo-types held by a society or community towards individuals or groups who deviate from perceived social norms or expectations"[8]. In other words, it is the disapproval of, or discrimination against, an individual or group based on perceived characteristics that serve to distinguish them from other members of a society. In this context, societal stigma encompasses the disapproval, judgment, and discrimination faced by women who choose or find themselves in the position of being single mothers. In societies that place a strong emphasis on the traditional two-parent family structure, single mother can be stigmatized due to cultural or societal norms that uphold the idea of the 'nuclear family'⁴ as the ideal or normal family unit. This stigma can manifest in various ways:

Negative Stereotypes

Single mothers may be subjected to negative stereotypes and assumptions about their character, moral values, and ability to parent effectively. They may be unfairly labelled as promiscuous, irresponsible, or unable to provide a nurturing environment for their children.

Single mothers face societal stigma due to cultural or societal norms that place a strong emphasis on the

the adults in a nuclear family are married. Cf., <https://www.britannica.com>, (accessed on 5th March, 2024).

traditional two-parent family structure. The fear of social judgment or stigma can influence the tendency to consider abortion as a way to avoid societal disapproval. Single mothers often face judgment and criticism from others who believe that parenting should occur within the context of married or partnered relationship. They may be looked down upon or seen as deviating from expected social rules and responsibilities.

Social Exclusion

Single mothers may experience social exclusion or isolation due to societal stigma. They may be excluded from social events, religious associations, marginalized in communities, or face limited access to support networks, which can further exacerbate feelings of loneliness and vulnerability.

Overcoming societal stigma towards single motherhood requires concerted efforts to challenge prevailing attitudes and beliefs. This can be achieved through education and awareness by creating awareness about the diversity of family structures existing in our society as a reality, and challenging stereotypes associated with single motherhood can help break down stigma and promote acceptance and understanding.

Building support networks and communities where single mothers can connect, share experiences and receive emotional and practical support can help combat feelings of isolation and marginalization. By promoting acceptance, and understanding, society can create an environment that supports and empowers single mothers, allowing them to thrive and provide a nurturing environment for their children.

Family Pressure

Family Pressure to undergo an abortion can stem from a variety of complex factors, including fear, shame, cultural norms, and economic instability.

"Often these women are also pressured into having an abortion by either their parents or their husbands. Perhaps the woman is in a bad marriage and her parents wish she would leave her husband, and, possibly, return home. They fear that if she has a baby, she will stay in the marriage" [2].

In this case, the pressure to abort is basically rooted in the family level where the enforcement to do it is from outside one decisions. From a Catholic perspective, families are called to support and uphold the dignity of every human life, especially the most vulnerable and defenseless. Encouraging abortion due to family pressure goes against the moral teaching of valuing and protecting the sanctity of human life from conception to a natural death.

Pressure from Boyfriend

Pressure from a boyfriend or partner to seek an abortion can create a coercive and manipulative

environment that undermines the freedom and agency of the pregnant women.

"Pressure to abort may come from the Father of the child, whether or not the couple is married. If they are unmarried, he may encourage abortion to avoid marriage or the responsibility of financial support for the child. He will support abortion to avoid telling his parents that he is the father of a child" [2].

In the Catholic understanding, relationships should be based on mutual respect, responsibility, and care for one another's well-being. Advocating for abortion based on pressure from a partner disregards the inherent dignity of both the unborn child and the mother and fails to uphold the values of love, respect and support in relationships.

Pressure from the Physician

Medical professionals play a crucial role in providing care and guidance to parents, including pregnant women facing difficult decisions.

"Through ultrasound testing and amniocentesis, doctors are better able to determine if the unborn child has any physical and mental disabilities in the very early months of pregnancy. Parents are faced with the decision of whether or not to abort their child if any of the numerous possible defects are found, from heart problems to Down's syndrome. ...The shame of giving birth to a defective child is a key factor in a couple's decision to have an abortion" [2].

Still yet in some occasions, women may opt for abortion because of her previous experience of giving birth to a deformed baby. According to Nancy Michel;

"Sometimes a woman is counselled to abort a fetus when she has previously given birth to handicapped child. She may not want to risk giving birth to yet another handicapped child, especially when the available tests cannot determine if the child will suffer from birth defects" [2].

Medical practitioners have a moral responsibility to uphold the sanctity of human life and to provide accurate information, support, and options that respect the dignity of both the mother and the unborn child. Pressurizing or advocating for abortion without considering all moral dimensions of the decision goes against the principles of medical ethics and the value of every human life

Unsuitable Time for Pregnancy

Majority of women aborting claim to be not ready to become mothers and be able to carry the maternal health challenges of the expectant and responsibilities of being a mother who raises a child, many will say I was not ready for that, and would sometimes abort without the knowledge of their partners. "In any case it does not confer any right to dispose of human life - even if embryonic- or to suppress it on the pretext that it is burdensome" [6]. Factors such as financial instability, schooling, lack of social support, or personal challenges

can contribute to a sense of being unprepared or overwhelmed by the prospect of pregnancy and parenthood.

"In many occasions when it comes to pregnancy, many women would say; it just was not a good time to have a baby. If one asked a group of pregnant women if this was a good time for them to have their babies, it is likely that most of them would say no. In their minds the best time is when we are financially secure and in a stable environment, preferably between the age of 25 and 35" [2].

In the Catholic moral teaching, every life is a gift from God and deserving of protection and care, regardless of the circumstances surrounding its arrival. Recognizing the inherent value of human life and providing support, resources, and compassionate guidance to individuals facing difficult circumstances can help address the pressure of untimely moments and promote life-affirming choices.

Physicians Oversimplification of the Procedure

When medical professionals oversimplify the procedure of abortion or fail to fully inform patients about its emotional, physiological, and spiritual implications, they may not be providing comprehensive and holistic care that respects the complexity of the decision at hand. Nancy Michel gives an example of a Nancyjo a woman who had an abortion and reported to have been told of the act as if it was such a simple and easy act *per se*. The Doctor told her that:

"I am going to take a little fluid out and put a little fluid in. You will experience severe cramping and that will be it. He did not tell her she would have to suffer through twelve hours of labor or face physical risks that ultimately left her infertile" [2].

Out of this Doctors' view on abortion a number of presumptions could be deduced. It is possible that the financial motive was involved into the act, that, provided the woman had money to pay for that forbidden act, that was enough to kill a fetus. From the Catholic point of view, individuals facing decisions about abortion deserve accurate information, compassionate guidance, and support that values the dignity of every human life involved. Oversimplifying the procedure of abortion can lead to misunderstandings, regrets and decisions made without full awareness of the moral and spiritual dimension at stake.

Conclusion

In conclusion the social causes of abortion among vulnerable populations particularly juvenile delinquents and those facing academic pressures, present a complex tapestry woven from various interrelated factors. The absence of comprehensive sex education and limited access to reproductive health services highlights systemic gaps that leave young individuals unprepared for the realities of sexual health

and responsible decision making. Moreover, societal stigma, neo-stereotypes, and family pressures reinforce the psychological burdens faced by those considering abortion, often compelling them to seek termination in isolation and fear of reprisal. Peer pressure and influence can further obscure the path to decision making that align with the Catholic church's moral codes, the personal values and the society at large.

The factors of single motherhood and the societal expectations tied to parenting amplify these dilemmas, as many young people find themselves navigating a precarious balance between personal ambition and societal judgement. Additionally, the oversimplification of the abortion procedure by healthcare providers can inadvertently downplay the physiological, emotional and psychological complexities associated with it, leaving individuals inadequately supported as they confront life threatening side effects.

Recognizing the multifaceted social motives surrounding abortion is critical not just for understanding individual experiences, but also for shaping effective interventions that promote reproductive health and empower young people. It is essential to advocate for comprehensive sex education, improved access to health services, and robust support systems that mitigate stigma and discrimination. By addressing these underlying social causes, society can create a more supportive environment that respects human life while at the same time promoting the well-being of all members, especially the most vulnerable.

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